

Unchaining Neoliberalism in Tanzania: “True Generosity of Sweden and Denmark’s Context-Specific Development Aid.

Musharaf Ali Talpur

University of Sindh, Jamshoro Pakistan

Hamadullah Kakepoto

Department of Sociology, University of Sindh, Jamshoro Pakistan

Macleans A. Geo-JaJa

Department of Educational Leadership

Shabana Tunio

Department of Sociology, University of Sindh Jamshoro Pakistan

ABSTRACT: Aid donors pursue a strategy of development about aid-recipients cultures contextualized as corrosive to development. This article, conceptualizing development aid as the outcome of aid-for-geo-strategic interests examines development aid in the context of “True generosity”. The article’s strong position is that post-Cold War aid is “development” that recaptures colonial lost grounds. In analyzing donor motivation in shaping development assistance, we show that aid failure lies in the falsity of the neoliberal framework that suffocates culture and the principle of Aid Effectiveness. In contrast, we determined that Sweden and Denmark’s context-specific development aid focused on intersectionality and heterogeneous forms does not serve as an experimental laboratory to destroy self-cultivation. Therefore, we show that the Swedish and Danish aid celebrate positivity through a horizontal dialogue, negating the myth that “barbaric” culture hinders development. In contrast to the celebrated donor approaches, the non-imperialist Sweden and Denmark’s The paper, therefore, contends that development aid that cedes ownership and expands human development indicators supplant “superior civilization”, the imperialism of development aid, and culture in development consistent with the 2005 Paris Development Aid Principle.

Keywords: Neoliberalism; Ownership; Quality Aid; Culture; Education; Development; Coloniality; Tanzania; Sweden; Denmark

Introduction

Development Cooperation Takeaways

Post-Cold War Development Aid Critique

Why does CONTEXT MATTER?

Sweden and Denmark in Tanzania In Education

Capacity Development in Tanzania: How Did Denmark Do?

Discussion, Lessons Learned, and Comments

References

True generosity consists precisely in fighting to destroy the causes which nourish false charity. False charity constrains the fearful and subdued, the "rejects of life," to extend their trembling hands. True generosity lies in striving so that these hands--whether of individuals or entire peoples--need be extended less and less in supplication, so that more and more they become human hands that work and, working, transform the world.
— Paulo Freire, Pedagogy of the Oppressed

1. Introduction

In the post-Cold War, many developing countries have experienced adjustment, austerity, and “coloniality of culture”. The monopoly of civilization, loss of cultural pluralism, and uniform solutions for plural societies have led to the nexus of development aid and development call for different approaches to development aid. The development cooperation that puts beneficiaries first and historicity at the center speaks to the argument of Deimperialization (rights in education). This paper will argue that shifting aid modalities from post-Cold War exploitation associated with unbalanced power relations between the periphery-center underpin the struggle to serve humanity from the ideological certainties and development aid as a poisonous gift. The dangers of development aid limitation on self-recreation are solutions when the solution is the problem (i.e. aid creating cultural depreciation and social disintegration). The shifting of aid modalities from the “truism” of development to post-materialistic goals contributes to this social and economic disintegration.

Development relations can be considered a means of enduring donor needs more than plural principles of human rights, shaping development in shared responsibility, and enlarging needs as valued by aid-receiving countries. As Geo-JaJa and Mangum (2003) and others have rightly argued, the ethical and political dimensions, as well as the scientific approach to development have failed as a substitute for a coherent development strategy. In standing the neoliberal scientific line of reasoning in its head, these authors point out that transplanting policies and institutions across countries with different historicity has failed. Their main point is that neither the World Bank nor the international development community that claims a privileged position in culture and knowledge can be trusted to bring about intrinsic aspects of freedom. To this end, characteristics or the practice of the single solution that was routinely invoked by donors to solve problems have not led to lives people have reason to value. There is more consensus about the falsehood of SAP which leaves wide open the question of what governments should do, with relatively less attention to how it has failed humanity with its disastrous consequences - poor countries lose power over their needs and control over their internal matters.

As Geo-JaJa and Mangum (2003) pointed out “mankind has not learned from structural adjustment programs and that simply mimicking the organizational forms of others is the root cause of the deep problems encountered in development countries. Neoliberal uniformity with its disastrous consequences for poor countries” marginalizes nations to overcome the established order and create an unequal relationship for safe guiding divides in development. As a result, its falsehood has continued to destroy development as aid beneficiaries have continued to lose power over their needs and control over internal matters. In advancing the argument of the indispensability of aid to “modernity”, we concentrate on the moral dimension of interventions in the practice of development aid, which systematically excludes those whose lives are most affected. Not only does this article explain delinking culture from development aid as the falsehood of neoliberalism in development cooperation, but it also makes a plea for a more genuine moral contestation involving beneficiaries who carry the brunt of the risk of the universalistic moral point of view of neoliberalism.

In this context, Swedish and Danish development practices that move beyond the opposition of culture in development and that reconstitute ethics in development expand and deepen the meaning and practice of self-development. In this context, as they recover the original meaning of development intervention, we argue that they leave no lives behind” (economically or culturally). In fact, unlike other aid donors that are insensitive to self-cultivation and cultural development, they incorporated cultural development in education and development within the country context, promoting ownership with no constraints on state power, therefore solidifying the foundations of their culture and indigenous capacities necessary for endogenous self-initiated development programs for well-being.

These two Scandinavian countries believe that the development of culture and cultural diversity is imperative in their international cooperation and saw culture in aid as a right and a duty for all peoples and all nations as they shared their knowledge and wealth with the people of Tanzania respecting their right of fundamental freedoms and duty to development their culture. This is central to development and takes the road of “bottom-up development” over top-down development. Their approach is characterized as more localized over a universally universal standard and prescription of development. In short, the culturalism of development aid and cooperation that legitimatizes and protects Human Rights Declarations, and promotes the Paris Declaration on Aid Effectiveness, and the Accra Agenda for Action meet development needs. These Declarations of sustainable humanity assign a larger focus on economically and societally sustainable development to developing countries in development processes. However, expanding globalization have engendered unprecedented opportunities to incorporate culture-centered thinking in development aid. Such imperative of associating the right to development and one’s own culture, respect for human rights, and identity is the greatest challenge of the falsehood of donor generosity and the ill of aid not anchored on a hybrid of economic and non-economic factors. Therefore, situating development aid within the donor cultural context is transmitting interventionist development that has become particularly irrelevant in the realm of internal socio-cultural dynamics.

The shortcomings of uniform policy prescriptions that can be applied across countries or subordination of culture are now evident in and widely accepted as human vulnerability and development imperialism have brought less hope. This intellectual project of the Global North that shaped new forms of shared responsibility gave rise to incompatibilities and contradictions of development discourse. In their development partnership in Tanzania, Sweden, and Demark have consciously chosen to abide by the Paris Declaration, a commitment to ensuring ownership, alignment of aid with the recipients’ development strategies, harmonization of actions, and greater country responsibility in project management.

Regardless of aid proliferation and commitment to international Declarations, the confusion of culture and multiple traditions of knowledge in a universal view is inherently misguided and necessary for critical understanding for lowering inequality in development. This means putting nations in the driver’s seat of development and making sure that people are active participants in the change process. Since meeting this challenge is more urgent

than ever today why do we join the debate and submit that development not cognizant of “culture” is “new colonialism” or imperialism and not national progress?

Contrary to the celebrated cultural universalism over being cognizant of cultural particularities as we know it, we put forward that the former represents part of the problem rather than part of the solution since the nation’s different historicity and specific contexts preclude mimicking magic potions of development policy. The implication for colonizing knowledge and cultural identity in development is the neglect that human life is conditioned not determined or developed as civilization or poison with a few deviations. This is an irreversible movement from an endless diversity of particularities to a world homogenized into the most arrangement-ordered arrangement that ignores the interplay of culture and knowledge sharing in promoting functioning livelihood (Marglin2003; Escobar 1995; Shanin 1997). In establishing the positional superiority of Western culture and “scientific” education became necessary as many commodities of colonial exploitation negated the wider extent of development. Such an approach of development aid without inclusive rights creates serious negatives on country-agency in development, particularly in education and cultural de-colonialization. That space of culture and knowledge tells a very potent story of the new colonialism through development aid relations.

In shading light to neoliberal donor policy of political capturing; rapid destruction of indigenous institutions and promoting non-development disguised as development, affirmed that what created the problem cannot be its solution. In exploring the role of the subaltern epistemological perspective, we will show that neoliberalism is ill-defined and ill-equipped to dismantle the dynamics of oppression and address social and cultural costs as well as the destruction of humanistic education. Indeed, these disparities in development cooperation are not only concerned with the upswing in globalization masked by low human development or cultural and development traps but reflect quite faithfully donor hierarchies of political power as a weapon of delocalization. In education, the hegemonic approach to aid-giving and its underlying principles becomes schooling to consume and universalization of expectation, which banish issues of culture and the right to the realm of “rights.”

In redrawing the world culture and knowledge systems map in development aid; post-Cold War era partnerships undermine the culture and development needs of aid recipients. Based on past lessons and current challenges, our thinking is that failure of development aid is reasoned by the arrogance of flexible positional superiority of the unknown that ignores the legitimacy of local histories, and cultures, and thinking differently to prefer own solution and understand risk. We remain skeptical that those who inhibit ownership and own reality of a development pathway are incapable of driving indigenous development (i.e. changing the lives of people in meaningful ways).

While in principle development pathways bear the potential of strengthening creative development it is worth noting that the prevailing human capital perspective emphasizes economic growth to the detriment of reference to broader human development and wellbeing. Such a growth-oriented framework, antagonistic to cultural development as well as the collective processes becomes a project of the self”. This is the unresolved problem of focusing on macroeconomic stability in development aid which has led to its rejection and call for a narrative cognizant of moving beyond traditional mainstream scientific articulation

to that which fosters economic growth combined with cultural and social dimensions of development that address power imbalance and fulfillment of human rights.

With the realization that neoliberalism in development cooperation has failed to promote pluralism and protect local economies from exploitation, why does the continued legitimization of their construct our understanding of global human rights discourses in development? The assumed cultural superiority and political power of donors that remain contestable lay at the center of development cooperation. In our belief, the instrumentalized role of culture as used in this article to mean the totality of patterns of behavior and belief that characterize a society cannot be discountenanced by the international development agencies. It is viewed as a necessary and sufficient element to bind people to one another economically, socially, and politically reducing ideological certainties and power differentials that engender balance in development. For instance, when elements of culture and human rights are delinked from education and development it corrupts education and destroys development capacities, thus nourishing the falsehood of development cooperation. Despite the undermining of people's faith in themselves and the belief that they can make it on their own, remarkably still no conscious effort is made to understand recipients' reality of modernity, their internal socio-cultural dynamics or to rethink the universal guideline to which recipients must conform.

Donor alignment with beneficiary development needs, cognizance of development capacities, acting on it, and the imposition of their values through cultural imperialism are the criteria used to evaluate Swedish and Danish education aid support to Tanzania. In this instance, they repudiated the universality of culture claimed by donors. This is "true charity" as their vision of development based on ethical principles expanded the opportunities that people have by enlarging choices and societal transformation, which could be expressed as the tolerance of development aid or a participatory form of development over the flowering of cultural imperialism. Cognizant of the Tanzanian development plan, intervention is firmly rooted in strengthening country systems with a strong commitment to ownership and taking cognizance of development capacity. In short, they acted to ensure that more and more of the "rejects of life" who are in supplication can become humans who work to transform their community. The obvious fact is that in; discounting a commoditized education model deficient in curriculum and content and unschooling of culture, they transmitted knowledge, attitude, and skills that go beyond working for the few - belonging to a capitalist society. From our perspective, this informality and criminality is not a response to people as human beings in privileged positions to attenuate despoiling or to bring themselves into a better life. We contend that development aid, if driven by mainstream schooling brings more harm than good to aid recipients and communities. People who thought the end of the Cold War would lead to sharing capitalism's love found out that they were wrong. They are wrong as progress has only manifested itself in the form of false generosity – bringing people into a disastrous present and future over a good life for all people. Morality is based on the belief in the "black box" (the blindness of universalism) that displaces internal socio-cultural dynamics, thus promoting the development of under-development disguised as development condemning aid-beneficiaries to artificial optimism. This is the question is Mainstream development bringing a better a better life to aid recipients? This is why scaling up aid activity to meet national needs never goes beyond perpetrating permanent founts of

donor false generosity nourished by the tension between donorship and ownership. This affirms that by relegating culture and other rights to the care of market forces, neoliberalism cannot dismantle the dynamics of imperialism.

When aid practice undermines culture and development capacity it is the tyranny of donor power that gives free reign to the imposition of epistemology in dialogue. Disruptive innovation and political concerns of development considered antithesis to effective socioeconomic functioning at all levels of society that undercuts location-based development need to be demolished. Paulo Freire, Amartya Sen, and Vanessa Andreotti make this very clear for us: they argued that the panoply of monopolies and a one-size-fit-all approach does not only translate political-economic systems across borders but also negates the fact that development can begin in any one domain and advertising or projecting hegemonic values as the development ethics that should govern culture and development discourse. A similar rejection of such development ethics and abstract moralizing discourse that inhibit in a significant manner other actors and approaches in development has been put forward by Geo-JaJa (2003) and Escobar (1995).

The process of reinvigoration of development that goes beyond trans-modernization requires unraveling incompatibility in development and calls, for a heterogeneous dynamic process of mutual transformation (i.e. contingent on historicity, ethics, and reality). Equally fundamental to this thinking is a move from a roadmap based on the violent exploitation with consequent “destruction” of economic life that led to the dismemberment of culture and development pluralism to an approach that all actors within a common framework. There is a variety of historical evidence of donor false generosity linked to uncritical generalization and unifying formulations of human conditions and inescapable tension in the development of prerogatives in partnership. This suggests that control and power structures set up during the colonial era are maintained today by universally defined rationality and irrationality as well as knowledge of development. There is little doubt that post-Cold War development is not a contingent narrative of different cultures and knowledge but manifests as universal in a problematic way. These identified realities and limitations of development are hidden colonial practices that failed to articulate development as freedom.

The ills of and failure of development aid is a denial of endogenous self-determination as an inalienable right (OECD 2005), as colonizers have their fixed recipients, biased to their ex-colonies rather than being dictated by educational or development needs. This forms literature of false generosity and the view that aid is unhelpful and even harmful to the development capacities and developmental growth of the recipient country. Easterly (2002) in *The Barren Land*, will argue that education aid is programmed to fail with growth in schooling disassociated with growth in the gross domestic product due to the politics of participation. The problem is more of context not the problem of geostrategic interests.

Gray (2013); Soderbaum and Brolin (2016) and Soderbaum, (2016:147) are conscious of the dual layers of ownership in development and cognizant of the apparent negatives of the neoliberal development pathway. These scholars pointed out that cultural capturing and control of relations by donors obstruct progress and create skills and knowledge required for the transformative development process. In addition, there is evidence cultural capturing mitigates comprehensive measures of “modernization” and

serves as a potential threat to country ownership and the recapturing of cultural pluralism and development pluralism in cooperation.

This article questions whether neoliberalism in development aid brings a better life to aid recipients. To develop the argument, examine the unintended side-effects of aid and why. The article builds on the growing body of research and documents how institutionalized hegemonic aid pushes for certain development practices. This triggers a larger debate on the unique place of culture in development, as well as the need for a rethink of aid donorship. Finally, the paper presents a discussion of Swedish and Danish education aid modality in Tanzania guided by complex matters of culture and sensitivity to local actors as consistency to three core components: consistency with Paris Principles for aid effectiveness; consistency with culture and indigenous knowledge and is cognizant of development needs and development capacities.

The importance of culture is not a propositional knowledge but a reality of the need to recapture the broad understanding of development aid - increasing education, employability, social empowerment, ownership, and participation. Other factors considered of positive influence on the MKUKUKUTA, a Swahili abbreviation for The National Strategy for Growth and Reduction of Poverty is giving space to participatory development over political participation and widespread belief in the “standardization of the mind”. In short, this universal cultural model does not focus on the marginalized and the extent of historicity and society that support rights in education. The cultural underpinnings that remain essential in rights in education are an energizing factor, which responds to specific contexts of Help People to Help Themselves. According to Quijano (2010); Mignolo et al. (2010) do not bring to light the history or the hidden story of the people without history (see also Mignolo 2007:7). Simply put, culture cannot be discounted by donors as this is the social glue that engenders equity in cooperation a prerequisite for self-actualization and understanding the violence of cultural Europeanization in development aid (Wu and Geo-JaJa 2016; Quijano 2010:23). Development as culture is the critical understanding and pessimism that development and progress are possible across socio-economic and heterogeneity of society. Accordingly, the knowing and being of aid donors should not become the universal fate of recipients of development aid.

Although aid-recipient cultures and economies have been destroyed in the name of development, reconstituting the “insurgent discourse of development” as a human responsibility, especially against the hegemonic intentions and relations of donorship is the necessary pathway for progress. Both Sweden and Denmark made a conscious effort to address the bleak consequences and impasse of development partnership. More importantly, they acknowledged and denounced immoral and unethical political motivations - the ills of donors’ imposition of external socio-cultural dynamics – as they made a conscious effort to engender oppositional thinking on a better two-way right path of development. Acknowledging the Swedish and Danish way of coping with the very concrete problem of claiming the universality of development and making sense of local realities helps to learn and move beyond the current specific debate.

The humanistic and life-oriented focus of Swedish and Danish education intervention within a global and national context, using various pedagogical frameworks, which offer

important lessons in the context of historical injustices, is argued to fit conveniently with the education budget support (GBS). The latter might not have all the expected positive effects but enhances livelihood improvement and attention to localized needs to address key concerns of beneficiaries.

Delinking ownership and majority participation in the process of development and denying equal rights and opportunities for the citizenry are threats to inclusive development and the political system and vanish the opportunity for all people to move forward together. Cognizant that people are increasingly separated by economic and political power, to reverse this dangerous trend in Tanzania, both countries understood that the nature of knowledge to be delivered cannot be considered an international public good nor can it be understood in the context of globalization, marketization and technology explosion. This cautionary note is important as developing countries are not globalized societies or technology societies, which enable people to benefit from their development efforts. If donors are not cognizant of these facts and the lack of local capacity to implement the MKUKUTA, no meaningful progress or cost-saving can result from development cooperation.

The content of development efforts and shift from project to program aid and ultimately to budget support for education to release the latent creative energy and improve the implementation of development activities among rural people for accelerated development is more adaptable to local initiatives and more participation. The result of such a process antithesis to econometric modeling is based on the standard evaluability criteria of the spread of benefits. At the heart of our elaboration of generosity-alienating verbosity in development aid is the distinction between contexts and driver(s) of both countries' aid-giving. Despite the focus on what guides the delivery of aid, we locate challenges to attaining commitment to the Paris Agenda and make suggestions on a pathway to adopting sensitivity to own needs and own development defined as "true" development generosity - improvement in the multidimensionality of poverty (see UNDP 2014).

2. Development Cooperation Takeaways

Regardless of the negatives or limitations of development aid, the donor community has delivered some positive results. However, the sustainability of the development gains depends on development capacities and consistency with the Paris Principles. However available evidence suggests that development aid failed because of the resulting hybrid socio-cultural combination, kaleidoscope of contradictions of interests and motives, and social engineering of development that neglects culture and fails to address the recipient's needs. This is why culture matters in development assistance.

Tanzania presents a case of comprehensive success of political will, as it was one of the first African countries to put together a comprehensive poverty reduction strategy. In general, for aid to be beneficial, the generosity and sincerity of donors must be front and center (see Berkin 2010; Brown et al 2014) and must not undermine the right to development (OECD 2011; Muntchick 2017); or lead to "so much ill and so little good". It is important to note that the defined limitations described in the forgoing are the results of

donor-vested self-serving interests (Geo-JaJa and Magnum 2003; Easterly 2004), a colonial process and its defining logic, which we refer to in this paper as coloniality invokes not only economic exploitation but also epistemic and cultural consequences. In clear terms, obvious is donor ambiguity on ownership, development capacities, and human rights characterize the history of “degrowth” and development trap, as aid did not address pressing development issues – human rights, capacity building, or lifting people out of poverty. In consequence, aid donors appeared at the wrong times with ill-conceived reforms and inappropriate practices that undermine progress.

Amartya Sen (1999) in the book titled *Development as Freedom* puts it, despite efforts by Pathway to build a strong and stable economy, the need for a framework that broadens development by capturing the influence of culture-specific histories and valued traditions of society) and context of politics explains ownership fosters national integration and enlarges opportunities for the citizens. In contrast, the Western European framework that sweeps culture under the carpet, whose purpose was never to bridge the gap between donors and recipients is development as underdevelopment or “development as freedom” denied. Contrary to the extant literature, the strength of this neo-colonialism intervention that fostered settler and indigene cultural tension and socio-economic inequality was stymied by the International Cultural Declaration, which was a step towards the defense of the non-universalism of cultures (see UNESCO, 1966), However, to the extent that Sweden and Demark delivered targeted and specific education aid in Tanzania is considered to be “enforced humanitarianism” as their collective conscience made it difficult for them to be passive bystanders of human multidimensional poverty sufferings.

As Eveline Herfken, founder of the UN Millennium Campaign and Special Advisor to the UNDP Administrator, stated hegemonic development aid is an element of imperialism and persisting colonial institutions, deep-rooted donor vehicles for reintegration into the imperialist world. Within this context contended therefore is that rich nations put roadblock after roadblock on ownership and development capacities’ that are considered critical instruments to address the root causes of multidimensionality of poverty and social construction of reality. If anything, donorship, even when successful—hardly made a dent in the lives of people. Why does the “Coalition of the Willing” not commit to implementing credible Paris Principles? Why is their check still on the way – as only Norway, Sweden, Denmark, and the Netherlands have met or exceeded the agreed standard volume of 0.7 percent of GDP for donor countries?

The choice to invent its epistemology, development pathway, and content of national development plan is the unique power of human rights, agency to wider consent, to non-state actors that take cognizant of development capacities in the local context for development (see Brolin 2017). Alienating verbosity in education failed development, as it tends to focus on human capital over human development a more powerful instrument that allows internalizing gains from development (OECD 2005; Ahmed 2011; UNDP 2013). More so, rethinking development and schooling in a local context is considered cooperation not driven by “development securitization, as it connects the centrality of culture and understanding that no one reality allows the contribution to the integral significance of dialogue (OECD 2005; Imperiale and Vanclay 2016:322).

Dialogue is not just about deepening understanding – but is a cooperative activity involving respect and non-violation of rights important to enhance inclusion and build social development that facilitates participatory development and human flourishing. In this understanding, the absurdity of neoliberalism is the violation of rights and the thinking that culture does not matter and therefore does not belong to development. This bold assertion of culture with the wrong characteristics, not the fulfillment of rights, which lie at the heart of aid repackaged and trade-off entitlements is nothing more than the 21st-century form of capitalist racism. This is the agitation that partnership itself needs to be rethought in line with the culture at the center of the local development agenda. This is the argument posed in this article that education needs to be rethought in line with the cultural vehicle for decolonizing the mind.

3. Post-Cold War Development Aid Critique

An exemplary work in this direction is Escobar (1988; 1985; 1995) and Freire (1973). They note that; neglect of internal socio-cultural dynamics and nourishing false culture coupled with a changing power environment undermine “truthful” dialogue and the greatness of historical civilization that play critical roles in pluralistic pathways to destroy false and misplaced humanness of development.

In a nutshell, the falsehood of neoliberalism is unilateral colonialism which does not capture the economic, cultural, political, and social pluralism on the ground. Donor generosity as a poisonous gift is the enemy of human development, not culture and local knowledge which we see as a necessary driver of non-alienating education for our development pathway. The point here is that development when done right requires engaging in “truthful” dialogue and reimagining new partnerships in a local socio-political context. Simply translated, recipients should get what they want regardless of incompatible donor objectives. Development must remain local and legitimize local control of the development process with a sense of history and need to enjoy their way of “modernity” (Hickey and Mohan 2005; Pretty 1995). Swedish and Danish frameworks firmly rooted in country-led plans, local histories local peculiarities made the education system work and meet critical social demands and needs. Therefore, as the article contended their framework addressed asymmetrical power relations that reimagine the culture of poverty, the subordination of people to the culture of “modernity”, and development functioning as an imperialist tool (McGillivray et al 2012; Brodin 2017), they enlarged economic and social opportunities and other developmental functions by increasing the quantity and improving the quality of education.

4. Why does CONTEXT MATTER?

While some scholars laud the increase in aid volume effective tool for development (Goertz and Powers, 2012), others argue that universalism of aid that shapes control over ownership is just as pervasive as colonialism or that aid is the development of underdevelopment as it perpetuates cultural and political imperialism. As Geo-JaJa and Mangum (2001) provide a compelling account of the World Bank/IMF conditionality puts it, World Bank/IMF SAP trumps moral objectivity gains of decolonization, but successfully

catalyzed donor geostrategic interests and the spread of imperialism of development (i.e. negation of the right to a culture which underpins human development and integrity of development). Stephen Browne in *Aid and Influence: Do Donors Help or Hinder?* Not surprisingly, we contend that while accountability is upward not downward; the rules of engagement, and content and terms of aid are stacked in favor of the donors.

William Easterly in questioning aid donors as creators of development characteristics of their generosity as a “poisonous gift” or a gift that constitutes a tempered version of crafting the neoliberal project of social and economic opportunities contradictions The challenge here is for the international aid to come to terms of not arrogantly believing that they are the storehouse of knowledge and superior culture. Overall, this might be attributed to the reason why the relative impact of development aid has been negative.

Coloniality partnerships without ownership and disillusion with neoliberalism

The international donor community has no regulating body. The closest semblance is the Development Assistance Committee (DAC) which serves as the voice" for OECD donors and a platform to discuss issues surrounding poverty reduction and development. Another institution of note is the UNDP which advocates support for principled development correcting the toxic tension of donorship and ownership and the universalization of development as modernity. Contrary to scholars who believe in the existence of a single culture, Amartya Sen in *How Does Culture Matter* points out the enduring power of culture in development and its important role as a driving force for social and economic transformation in societies (Sen 2004), is closely related to subjecting education to the logic of rights in education that rebalance commodification, and revitalize local community actors' participation (i.e., reordering power and agency in the growing complexity of society). Conceptualizing culture as intricate for development illustrates that culture is central to ownership and social rights, as development is more than economic growth or expanding opportunities against the background of economics.

Elsewhere, the first author in another publication has argued that the discourse of Structural Adjustment Program SAP, particularly in Africa, suffers from three major deficits: several steps as cultural colonialism. it involves disrespect of culture and sovereignty thus, involves one nation acting on another, but rather nations working with each other; fails to address the consequences of history and is oblivious to the politics of cultural universalism provoking widespread economic tension and protest (Geo-JaJa and Mangum 2003).

In several works, Paulo Freire articulated that cultural universalism is a major source of development of underdevelopment and cultural defoliation. The latter does not give room to deepening self-actualization and development as freedom understanding Paulo Freire further argued the political nature of development devoid of dialogue that destroys Indigenous culture and political systems in the following words:

Disruptive donor generosity and powerful ideology of anti-dialogism that not only destroy ownership and participation but also portray people as helpless victims and see culture as corrosive to local society as a whole is the negation of people's ontological vocation to be more fully human (Freire 1970).

The above quote underpins the need to understand where people are coming from, where they are going, and why they should buy into dangerous economicism and counterproductive penetrating epistemologies that question “true development generosity. Thus, for C. Wright Mills the merits of development aid promoting development is the mythicizing of reality and a product of the failure to cede ownership and agency in development:

“Freedom is not merely the opportunity to do as one pleases; neither is it merely the opportunity to choose between set alternatives. Freedom is, first, the chance to formulate the available choices, to argue over them -- and then, the opportunity to choose (C. Wright Mills 1959, 174).”

Another complexity of the ills of aid is imperialism (a mix of economic, sociocultural, technological, and political influences).

These authors Easterly (2005); Kanbur (2000) and Escobar (1995) contend interventions that universalize culture and undermine human rights as colonialism repackaged are the problem, not the presumed cultural characteristic. As a result, the ill of development aid without culture is imperialism (a mix of economic, sociocultural, technological, and political influences). Yet humanity is asked to be faithful to a failed project of the social construction of unsustainable consumerism over an alternative pathway that reorders power and development cooperation – ownership and other economic and cultural rights that subject development to the logic of the community (UNESCO 2011; UNICEF 2006). In this vein, unpacking intervention limitations requires scrutinizing the context of a sector-wide approach or stand-alone project aid. The above reality is an illustration that partnerships can settle ownership if cognizant of a location-based approach that rules out any universally optimal development aid.

Is Donorship Colonialism Repackaged?

In contrast to the literature that shows Official Development Assistance (ODA) as paternalistic, this article will argue that donorship contributes to several indicators of economic and social precariousness. These disadvantages are illustrative of the anti-dialogic framework often correlated or associated with repressive donor-repressive cooperation. The deficit of putting less emphasis on benefactors' rights is the socioeconomic cost of colonialism repackaged - citizens filled with global narrations and nations giving up control of knowledge - is undermining processes of development originating from the bottom (a similar argument is developed in Easterly (2005); Geo-JaJa and Mangum (2003); and Mills (1959).

One can safely assert that donorship as development is associated with the fulfillment of human rights and conscientization requires reinvigorating vital development capacities for development (see Hansen and Tarp 2000; Kanbur 2006; and Marglin 2003). The danger of donors' insensitivity to aid recipients' peculiarities and histories is that even when countries are provided with the opportunity to act on available choice discursive practices; the disconnect associated with cultural universalism and the failure to reimagine traditions and reinvent social value becomes the doom of own development pathway,

The importance of the above point is that development aid works. But we contend that it can lead to reclaiming ownership, crowding out effects of geostrategic interests, and deepen and not corrode self-determination. Furthermore, unpacking aid as colonialism or overcoming the economic poverty and social exclusion of globalization support the practice of communalism only when human rights, substantive freedom, and agency equity are integral and captured in donor moral imperatives to engage in development rooted in precepts of pluralism (McGillivry et al 2012; McGillivray et al. 2016).

David Landes, the great Harvard economic historian, joined in with his bold assertion that: "If we learn anything from the history of economic development, it is that culture makes almost all the difference" (Landes, 2000:2). Ake (1982:128) and Sen (2004) in stressing that cultural adjustment program is dangerous, argue that it is the worst inhumanity of what is called development racism. We pose that since culture is an intricate part of our lives, one ill of aid will be development aid with culture or the imposition on recipients of aid regardless of their internal socio-cultural dynamics the imposition of external epistemologies. This reasoned for the belief that promoting and protecting cultural rights is more important than expanding aid volumes through imposed cultural adjustment programs. So, there you have it, undoubtedly aid without culture or without an understanding of the culture of the people donors seek to help, the impact is social entrapment and development crisis. There is something wrong when aid is packaged without an understanding of the local culture or situated within the cultural context. Simply put, aid packaged or imposed on recipients is another form of colonialism - a kind of moral deficiency embedded in false donor generosity reflected in cultural adjustment programs.

Widening and Deepening participation in Aid Partnerships

The reality of the bold assertion "We will Save Africa and "We will end world poverty," Could either be interpreted as donor concern for the well-being of all people or the myth of cultural and knowledge superiority - the contradictions of imperialism oversimplification of reality. Such deep-seated vested interests lead to denial of deficiency in rights to ownership of development Eveline Herfkens, Executive Coordinator, UN Millennium Campaign strongly explained the insensitivity and falsehood of traditional aid claims to "knowing it all" in this bold assertion:

Traditional technical assistance has tended to supplant local capacity, undermine local knowledge and institutions, and render recipient countries more vulnerable and dependent on aid. The reasons for these shortcomings are legion. Donor-driven projects are not derived from aid recipients' development priorities and are an expression of an attitude by donors that "they know better (see UN 2008:1).

We submit the falsification of donor generosity constitutes the absence of the moral obligation to understand the need to reorient donor motives. In more specific terms, donor interests isolate community economic and socio-cultural challenges render them dependent on donor aid, and limit aid to wider purposes. Thus, the extent of subjugation and supplication is the imperialist reengineering cooperation and prioritizing one set of rights over ethical and moral obligations in development, thereby limiting alternative options

meaningful to mitigate cultural and development continuities. Why then is neoliberalism whose interest is culture and political capturing to supplant local capacities and institutions still donor donor-favored roadmap wherever they have intervened? Aid effective or donor success is culture-development aid programming that takes cognizance that “All human rights are universal, indivisible and interdependent.”

Even if donors do not know what should be done, they should understand that they have the moral obligation to stop and challenge the imposition of the falsehood of disruptive conditionality and practices by situating education and development activities in the lived experience of countries. In this respect, the whole new relationship of power that emerges around the world of cooperation opens a series of possibilities that have the possibility of generating new ways of naming and acting in the aid-recipients world. This that we argue that underpinning Sweden and Denmark's cooperation in Tanzania resulted in the “development of hope” not the “development of oppressed.” In sum, cognizant of the “donor-practice of universalism” that renders beneficiaries more and more in supplication and nations not able to help themselves suggested is an approach with active participation and ownership by the people.

Education Dogmatism in Aid Commodification

Most studies that investigate education aid in developing countries concluded that it has mixed results (Michaelowa and Weber (2007). Even some studies question the extent of education aid on social and economic development due to the obvious stagnation in poverty eradication and literacy. It is against this wider context that this section gives currency to the high cost of alienating verbosity in education. Neoliberal dogmatism in the context of education which is corporative undercut rights in education (Geo-JaJa and Mangum 2002a:97; 2003:315), while also infringing on development pluralism. Such a construct of education not supportive of indigenous knowledge or learner creativity regards people as adaptable and manageable beings with minimal critical consciousness to intervention in the world as transformers of that world. Banking Model of Education” an anti-dialogical epistemology full of perfidy a dehumanizing framework of dialogue and reflection on reality stands in opposition to providing the relevant knowledge and skills, and attitudes for the approximate majority of citizenry who remain in the periphery and semi-rural communities. Moreover, education that recolonizes people's minds inhibits creativity by isolating consciousness and awareness from the locals (Freire 1973). Those that confirm differential development and explain why nations fail is the call to international actors and institutions to pause and radically rethink what it is that makes a humanistic globalization (Stiglitz 2000:17-24). This is the urgency of decoloniality, on one hand, to decolonize the imagination of the dominated (Quijano 2010:23) and deglobalization on the other to unremitted control over the production of knowledge and subjectivities (Easterly 2002). In our opinion, oppressive cards of power in education that shape the kind of education that impede the autonomous path of development and practice of difference necessitate reimagining relations in development aid partnership. This attempt to move away from a “Vertical Partnership” (Top-down with conditionality) to a partnership rooted in a “Horizontal Partnership”, based on trust, mutual benefit, and equity should be the new alternative way to do development partnership.

It is important to repeat that education viewed as universal and constitutive of coloniality reorganizes perception and consciousness and underscores development aid repackaged as poison. Indeed, education repackaged for globalization which cannot buy freedom underlines the significance of a bottom-up framework that provides an opportunity to achieve rights in education (Wu and Geo-JaJa 2016) and the right to development (human rights and freedom). When education exists as a pluriverse comes hope for every learner to enjoy the elements of availability, accessibility, adaptability, and acceptability in education – localized knowledge consistent with reality-driven aid for inward realistic solutions.

But when articulated in less alienating verbosity opens up the floodgate to different cultures and facilitates people making sense of their world (see Babaci-Wilhite et al 2012; Hall, & Rosenberg, 2000; Freire 1973). Again, Wu and Geo-JaJa (2016) note that reductionism in resizing value as an ontological element that remains outside of orthodoxy embraces all the principles of rights in education. The latter portends creative thinking for collective and organized action for community development against an epistemic mold that treats education as a commodity. Indeed, the singularity culture that characterizes mainstream epistemology failure forecloses the main extent of education, leaving no space to challenge pervasive ideological dogmatism practices that led to cultural entrapment. (see Wu and Geo-JaJa 2016).

Aid commodification seems even more complex, as neutralizing the universal construct of education is considered a “poisonous manna” of cultural imperialism that destroys cultural identity and epistemic diversity (Marglin 2003; Geo-JaJa 2006; Mamdani 1993, 15). Furthermore, as pervasive aid leaves economicism untouched, education is simply a function of having enough schools not as freedom in the context of Katarina Tomasevski 4As (2001:12-13). For us, the validity of education commoditization is the logic that: “No development [exists] without sensitivity to local knowledge and no enlarging of opportunities [exists] without contextualizing education beyond the conventional definition of culture and human rights premised on alienating verbosity that foregrounds the human as an autonomous individual/agent unyoked by the surrounding world. Thus, the reason for arguing for rights in education is an understanding of culture and rights, beyond the dogmatism of education commodification that naturalizes culture and indigenous knowledge. To say the least hegemonic reforms that validate alienating verbosity practices support a single notion of “modernity”, consequently it does not allow the discovery of cultures and knowledge. This new form of colonial education practice leads to the atomization of individuals and commodification of spheres of life, as it undermines local knowledge that epitomizes reality.

5. Sweden and Denmark in Tanzania In Education

Sector Intervention: A Way out of Aid Quagmire

Sweden and Denmark's education support in Tanzania cognizant of development needs coalesce around the Paris Principles. Furthermore, their alignment of aid with the MKUKUTA plan explains their 1 and 2 ranking in the Commitment to Development Index

(see Center for Global Development 2018). The United States ranked 23 of 27 behind other OECD countries that did not do brilliantly as its current practice contracts the 1973 Foreign Assistance Act – involving intended beneficiaries in the planning and implementation of project effort, as well as in the gains of development.

No lip service for Sweden and Denmark's strategy of relocalization with radical interrelatedness, openness, and plurality, "left nobody behind" as it enabled beneficiaries to develop organically to the dictates of their developments (Odén and Tinnes 2003) and build on existing local reality. Therefore, seeding intervention with diversity and guided by the broader new rights in education transformed portfolios of human assets for self-determination and gives hope to the "rejects of life" most often excluded by the Cultural Adjustment Programs (CAP) to be involved in actions that enhance their happiness or the good life. In more general terms productive participation or proactive involvement essential for human development is conditional in the ways cooperation is structured or in the conditionality of reform. Unlike traditional donors who deliver innocuous and malignant aid (Selbervik and Nygaard 2006: 86; Gates and Hoeffler 2005); in short-circuiting education's positivity to broader development (see Molenaers and Renard 2009; Penny et al. 2008), they both encouraged the widest possible active participation of local stakeholders and national non-government organizations in the development process. This local signpost of development intervention that shifts from universal principles of freedom (Lasonen et al 2005; UNESCO 2011) to participation in local rights of education refutes the myth that "barbaric culture hinders development." Both countries ebbed the moral ethics of development as culture.

In liberating Tanzania communities from Eurocentrism, they localized education aid as diverse, and turned such diversity into a rallying point for construction that supports deepening MKUKUKU and localization of "modernity." The key questions that need to be addressed are: did they cede control of the development pathway to the Tanzanian people; do they understand the strategic value of culture and development capacities that unsettle anti-dialogical epistemologies and restore threatened ways of knowing? If these interrogations show that development assistance is delivered in a manner cognizant of Tanzania's development needs and consistent with the Paris Principle, both countries' development cooperation will succeed. In the next section, Swedish and Danish education intervention in Tanzania is understudied.

Lessons learned from Sweden and Denmark development cooperation:

Post-Cold War saw a significant change in development aid sign-post signpost. But that was not the case for Sweden, whose development cooperation objective remained to create opportunities for the "Rejects of Life" and people who live in poverty and discriminated against to improve their living conditions. Development cooperation that is based on the principles of aid and development effectiveness, and the new agreements reached by the international community in 2015: the 2030 Agenda, the Addis Ababa Action Agenda, and the Paris Agreement focused on ownership and strengthening development capacities necessary for creative own development that enlarged opportunities for women and youths (Government of Sweden 2010; Sida 2015). Unlike other donors not motivated by geostrategic interests and ideological transmission for either acculturation or

assimilation, Sweden strengthened employability, increased entrepreneurship, and access to capital for more than 1 million small businesses through new improved “broader education” opportunities,

The novelty of Swedish aid anchored on diverse approaches to a single development destination is for “flowering the world” as opposed to “flowering Sweden” (Soderbaum 2017; Government offices of Sweden 2010). This is that which distances them from the myth of rich capitalist donors that provide educational support grounded in alienating verbosity. In short, education support is defined by: (i) participation and empowerment (ii) quality learning and knowledge indigenization, (iii) gender equity and empowerment, and (iv) human security underpinned by development as culture-empowered women and the “rejects of life” to work and working, transform their world.

Swedish education support focused on adult illiteracy, improving schooling and learning opportunities at all levels, and strengthening the development capacities required for the success of MKUKUTA. In this vein, it partnered with the Tanzanian government to establish the Folk Development College, Institute of Adult Education, and National Correspondence Institution, and technical education that contributed to or strengthened individual and institutional capacity for self-reliance and community self-development. These educational programs typically adopt the traditional roadmap of education to provide life skills needed to create opportunities for securing a livelihood or building wealth.

For instance, the Private Agricultural Sector Services (PASS) program extended loans to 56000 projects and created millions of jobs in rural areas (see also Brown 2-017; Brolin 2017:1), Support provided to the Kibaha Education Centre strengthened entrepreneurial skills, financial and project management skills, health maintenance and management skills, and administrative capabilities cognizant with development capacities necessary for local, national and international commitment to the implementation of MKUKUTA. Furthermore, they all delivered demand-driven technical capabilities to respond to the pressing illiteracy and income poverty of rural farmers. Probably, the most significant support is to the Primary Education Development Program (PEDP) which made a huge difference in meeting the right to education (schooling) as Tanzania continues to face challenges in rights in education.

A mapping of Swedish education sector support to scholarships, research grants, postgraduate programs, and PhD training done in harmonious consistency to government ministries and universities' development capacity needs (see Sida 2015; Freudenthal 2014) created a wealth of invaluable research capacity among many senior officials in government Ministries and universities that have come to play a major role in the design and implementation of the MKUKUTA. For instance, the lead author of the MKUKUTA is a professor in the Economics Department who has been supported with postgraduate study in Sweden.

Swedish universities have continued to collaborate with local universities to develop high-quality PhD training programs through co-curriculum development and co-supervision of PhD students which has led to carrying out research in many fields and training many university and government staff to PhD degrees (Freudenthal 2014). For instance,

cognizant of the inadequate research capacity at the university, they acted on this cognizance and supported the University of Dar es Salaam and the Think Tank COSTECH to create a wealth of invaluable research capacity and contributed to more than a thousand trained university researchers who facilitated the development of more than 6871 firms which improved both revenue and employment of youths and women.

The study by Sida, (2015) and Freudenthal (2014) summed up support success in this manner: "A large majority of beneficiaries are deeply engaged in research with direct relevance to poverty reduction and the development of Tanzania. They consider themselves to contribute not only to developing relevant research results, but also have made significant contributions to community outreach activities, extension work, public service, innovation clusters, and in creating entrepreneurs (Freudenthal, 2014:20). Clearly, their results are consistent with our review support the conclusion that Swedish support to Tanzanian built universities-built research capabilities, developed PhD programs and trained PhDs enhanced availability and efficient use of knowledge, research, and technology as tools for increased productivity.

That which can be deduced from the above facts is that alignment with the Paris Principle in facilitating a better understanding of the local socio-cultural and political context of MKUKUTA and existing capacities overlooked by other donors, made Swedish education support a success as it created an enabling environment (cultural sensitivity) that improved factors that drive attainment of the MKUKUTA. Therefore, we contend that the Swedish partnership is considered appropriate and sustainable and aligned to the country-led plan with Tanzania leading the JAST group to meet commitment to the Paris principles.

This analysis provides evidence that Sweden's education sector linked directly to MKUKUTA through GBS strengthened institutional research capacity, positively affecting development capacities and sustainability of the MKUKUTA outcomes. Alignment with the Paris Agenda not only fostered developmentally effective aid it also reduced the tension of donorship and ownership. The reality is that despite the ambiguous literature on aid effectiveness, Swedish education support in Tanzania in redefining education alienating verbosity, cognizant of the central of culture in development that culture matters and delivering aid in a manner cognizant of inadequate research and development capacity and engaged in cooperation in a manner that balanced positives brought back hope robbed them by the falsehood of neoliberal generosity.

6. Capacity Development in Tanzania: How Did Denmark Do?

Denmark in Tanzania

Danish education Support has been and still is relevant to the development goals and needs of the government of Tanzania. Danish exceptional approach sensitivity to culture, cognizance of development capacities, and alignment with the MKUKUTA give space to country ownership. In the CDI Denmark is ranked just behind Sweden. These distinctive attributes demonstrate the positiveness of targeted sectoral support to national development priorities. For example, like Sweden, Denmark balanced human rights and culture with development - - "where no one is left behind." Driven by the motto: "Helping

Nations Help Themselves, they made significant inroads in the social sector in Tanzania, giving space to people to 'set their life objectives and define their strategies for Freedom from Poverty and Freedom to Change pillars of self-determination (see Denmark's new rights in education strategy in Tanzania Midtgaard 2013).

Guided by Tanzania's country-led strategy, education was provided as a non-static commodity (i.e. not in isolation from the reality that culture makes a huge difference), which makes it possible for all people to unleash their potential as drivers of community sustainability. For instance, education support through GBS strengthened ownership; improved development capacities, and empowered communities, thus ensuring that the rural poor do not continue to suffer from multidimensional Poverty.

Unlike traditional donors whose conflicting motive is to expand their economic and geostrategic interests, The Danes focus on strengthening research capacity of high quality and relevance to participatory development and at the same time systematically emphasize addressing Paris Principles and the core development capacities required for the MKUKUTA. Education support over the years strengthened PhD programs, supported PhD training, and knowledge sharing and research collaboration which enhanced local research capacity.

In addition, investments in skill development programs like Vocational Education and Training and innovative education packages increased participation, awareness, utilization of public entitlements, and increased social networks, self-confidence, and mobility of women which underwrote development. The collective voice of women positively affected the following main pathways: (1) the generation of income through bridged gender-based discrimination, (2) the improvement of agriculture contributed to improved livelihood and community development, and (3) building capacity contributed to employability, empowerment of youths, and mitigated negative effects on women's economic and political entrapment. Support went a long way to making possible access to resources (such as credit and training), exposure to group support, and accumulation of social capital which led to positive social and psychological empowerment of women.

Denmark's aid modality is distinguished by the centrality of the right to culture, rights in education, and right to development depoliticize individuals or entire peoples need to be extended less and less in supplication, so that they can again become human hands which work to claim own development.

In short, partnered initiatives and policies not only improved the culture of poverty and reduced the risk of social breakdown by attacking the factors that push citizens into marginality and out of functionality in their respective communities; it also mitigated intergenerational reproduction of poverty for a significant portion of Tanzanians. Selbervik (2006: 9) noted that the collective rights of beneficiaries to self-determination and enlarged opportunities normalized social disqualification, economic vulnerability, and human deprivation. These positives protect individual rights against precarious living standards by bridging income disparities (Denmark 2014).

The lesson learned from the above articulation is that (1) the rights in education approach protects citizens from the risk associated with social disaffiliation and supplication; and (2) securing it contributes to their pathway to escape human poverty and culture of poverty. We submit, therefore, that without culture in development cooperation, aid volume will only supplant participation and ownership as it creates parallel systems that undermine formulating policies, development capacities, and national development strategies.

7. Discussion, Lessons Learned, and Comments

The trust of this paper is to evaluate the consistency of Swedish and Danish development intervention in Tanzania as “True generosity” from the perspective of trans-cultural dialogue and integral self-development. Although there has been much debate in the literature about the relationship between aid support and development, econometric analysis shows mixed results. But Swedish and Danish Education budget support in Tanzania, in going beyond the donor disruptive intervention model with its ideology of anti-dialogism, in reconstituting development as a shared responsibility challenged neoliberal result-oriented development intervention and prioritized support to Tanzania government with the provision of budgetary support. In short, both countries reconstituted development intervention in appropriate dialogical practice, which involved establishing respectful relationships and practicing intervention as a shared responsibility, and between attentiveness to self-actualization and attentiveness to ethical dimensions of development.

This article examines the Swedish and Danish education aid to Tanzania and the mainstream consensus defined by OECD. First, the article suggests that Aid volume alone is not the moral attestation that matters for not “to leave no one behind” legitimized by country values and cultural pluralism. Second, our analyses reveal that mainstream development cooperation attempts to balance geostrategic objectives and developmental accountability pose challenges to ownership and aid effectiveness. Thus, this article confirms the evidence that achieving sustainable benefits requires sustainability ownership and a commitment to address a wide range of cultural and human rights matters. Our strong position is that even with a high volume of aid cooperation without cognizance of culture and alignment to a nation’s development needs the falsehood of donor generosity and the failure of development aid lifts more people from the unfavorable hostility of supplication and the imperialism of development. Furthermore, this article confirms the positiveness of culture (what we call the reality) and the negation of positional superiority in Swedish and Danish aid-giving in Tanzania.

In fewer generality terms, speaking in one voice and power and situating development within the context of the country empowered and built the development capacities of the “rejects of life” and women whose freedom has been exploited. On average, with indigenously oriented development, Tanzanians become less poor and less in supplication, as the number of people increased because of the generosity of aid foundation on their Indigenous knowledge which is embedded in their culture. This is the lesson that culture makes all difference as it engulfs our lives, our happiness, and our freedoms, thus it can reliably ensure that the “rejects of life” who have been supplanted in development are extended out of supplication to transform the world. The phenomenal success of the

Marshall Plan, but the current concept and construct of aid is unhelpful or is even said to be harmful to the needs of the recipient country, as donors have genuine interest only in cultural imperialism.

To sum up, a few key factors that underpin the international Donor community trends are highlighted as lessons learned:

- Development cooperation can make an enormous difference if/when problematized in the appropriate policies and cognizant of cultural peculiarities that do matter for effective development cooperation.
- Incorporating local capacity building and proven country-driven know-how as an integral element of activities is one way to address the tension between donorship and local ownership.
- Support for education and research capacity illustrates shifts from project to budget support: aligned to MKUKUTA and a development need enhanced Multidimensional poverty impact.
- Development aid that undervalues local epistemologies but is guided by colonial-like disruptive and dysfunctional practices fails to unlock education's "wider human purposes and right to self-development.
- Non-neocolonialist education that cedes control to local actors and integrates culture that matters into development condenses cooperation complexities and "leaves no one behind."
- Donor behavior and greed hinder the fullness of development aid and thwart self-help capacity to uproot imperialism's desired direction.
- Even with intensifying imperialism development modality rooted in the social-relational continuum and cultural pluralism will create vibrant local-voices local voices to address distortions and systemic impediments.
- Throwing more aid at recipients is not the most effective means for development capacity for participatory development, creating space for locals to take charge of control of socioeconomic, sociocultural, and goal-oriented development projects is a success.
- The "single story" of the development aid approach not only "imprison imprisons;" at best it erodes culture and overrides development. Another notable important lesson is that the moral understanding of our experience and historicity is the effectiveness of development intervention.

In a nutshell, critics (e.g. Quijano 2010; Mignolo 2007; Frank 1966; Fanon 2007) highlight that pluralism of development aid is indispensable for the many-sidedness of development and should be complemented rather than replaced by aid universalism. However, there is consensus that internal accounts of education remain the foundation of individual and collective imaginations. The requirements for understanding contemporary global and local realities also tend to strengthen links between education and human emancipation and education and development. the historical evidence is surely that the coloniality of aid will have to address emancipatory development and the challenges of coloniality propensities. The challenge of coloniality in modern terms is the domain of

development aid that allows the creation of wealth shaped by systemic attacks on Indigenous knowledge and ways of being.

When aid is managed well or when interpreted as moral ethics or when truth and love guide the conduct of partnership, local actors become an integral part of development expressed as modernization/Westernization as they manifest across globalization. The latter is situated within local historicity as culture is not discounted by donors as they see its obvious relevance to development realities. In this vein, we strongly submit that culture matters in development and that the failure of aid scaling up to catalyze development is the result of “cultural bomb” programs that accelerate the loss of hope either coopt local needs or that do not reflect the reality on the ground as they portray indigenous culture as “barbaric” and corrosive to development. This which we consider the “new colonialism” or imperialism that imposes alienating values and interests is not development. This article takes the position that development assistance when/if delivered in a manner cognizant of the lived experience of developing countries opened possibilities that generate new ways of naming and acting in respective societies and cultural pluralism that have the power to transform the reality of beneficiaries into the hope we note.

The failure of development aid cannot be attributed to “barbaric cultures or corruption as the success of Sweden and Denmark’s aid in Tanzania refutes this rationale. Both countries understood that culture gives partners the freedom and ability to reflect upon their realities and critical thinking to recognize their incompleteness and find solutions to transcend their limitations, thus, they undertake rights and culture-based development, to better manage local human and cultural resources in Tanzania. benefitted from culture-based economic development. Their modern brand of development aid differs from that of the ‘colonialist’ wherein aid programs were meant to dominate and battle with each other to exploit “pieces” of local wealth. The right to development aid as self-determination—was realized by a love for wisdom, and by recognizing 1) the extraordinary productiveness of Tanzanians, and 2) the capacity of decentering to guide development against the corrosive hegemony of power, but to affirm the right to self-development, particularly Africanization on the grounds of sovereignty as they invested in the arts and crafts and creative industry sectors. In moving away from a universalized conception of humanity driven by reconstruction of identity they did not silence knowledge, voices, and human rights, as they incorporated all of life’s dimensions and the voice of partners whose capacities, and whose members are called to contribute towards and share in the benefits of development.

Development aid is important. It helps to solve social and economic problems and thus can bridge the inequality gap between and within countries. On the contrary, the cumulative wider effects of development aid are minimized by universalization and the call to dismiss all practices that aim at improving the human condition. To meet the needs of development or to ameliorate the results of asymmetrical relations, donors must not know better what the people need than the people themselves. In rethinking the abstract collective dimension of culture or by understanding that different civilizations have shared contents the centrality of democratic participation and ownership legitimacy is imperative. This is why we argue that Modernization/Westernization undermines multi-valued development pathways as proclaimed by the UN’s Economic and Social Council (see

UNESCO 1966; 1986). That which is not in dispute is that the darker side of coloniality in development monopolizes partnerships, controls revolutionary social transformation, and violates the collective dimension of development knowledge. Thus, it can be argued that the development aid with Eurocentrism, and depoliticized with universalism should be abandoned. In context, Swedish and Danish interventions that recognize the centrality of the cultural dimension of development without dangerous effects are without global modernity and global coloniality. Accordingly, this informs the authors' belief in development cooperation conceived in a deeper understanding of cultural diversity, particularly those linked to development as an instrument of sustainability, construction of reality, and positive social change. The central argument is that the complete range of social, cultural, and economic opportunities manifestations of unity, and above all homogenizing development aid and legitimizing oppressive partnerships affirms the flawed discourse of development in the singular.

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